

Research methodology

Use of the chlorophyll meter in N management of subtropical wheat following rice

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In South Asia, researchers have reported that the highest wheat yields can be obtained by splitting the recommended N dose of 120 kg N ha⁻¹. For two splits, basal N at land preparation and an N topdressing at crown root initiation (CRI) or 20-25 d after sowing (DAS) are applied. Additionally, N is sometimes added in a third dose at maximum tillering (MT) or jointing. The CRI and MT stages are times of irrigation, so the N fertilizer is applied just prior to irrigation to improve efficiency of N.

Since N fertilizer topdressings are linked to irrigation at CRI and MT, options for topdressing at other times are limited. This practice is quite different from flooded rice culture where N topdressings can be applied at virtually any time. Using a chlorophyll meter in wheat culture, therefore, might have a role not in the timing of N topdressings but in determining whether a topdressing is needed or not, and, if so, possibly to predict how much. This prediction would be most important in the third split at MT because, depending on soil N supply, date of planting, and seasonal temperatures, N supply going into the reproductive stage of subtropical wheat may often suffice. The topdressing at MT can be evaluated as treatments with and without the application. Chlorophyll meter readings can be made on the day of MT topdressing and the "grain yield response" can be plotted against SPAD (soil-plant analysis development) readings. The critical SPAD reading for MT would be that corresponding to the

least significant grain yield response determined by LSD at P=0.05.

Evaluating the response of topdressing of wheat at MT with the chlorophyll meter is probably best done in farmers' fields where a large variation in available N in the soil at MT exists. Doing this study on station probably requires a range of basal N and CRI N to ensure "deficiencies" in the lower basal rate treatments at MT. Additionally, by varying the amount of N topdressed at MT, we can see whether the chlorophyll meter prior to application can "predict" the N rate when it "predicts" a deficiency. Taking soil samples at the time of MT for exchangeable NH₄ and NO₃ would give additional information related to the need for N at that time. Inorganic N at harvest would be important to know as well since it might be present if MT N is applied when it is "not needed." The SPAD reading at MT in wheat, therefore, may have a role in minimizing residual NO₃ at harvest which would be lost to denitrification or leaching when the field is flooded for rice.

A preliminary field trial evaluating the use of the SPAD meter for determining the need for MT N was conducted at Ludhiana, Punjab, India, in the 1996-97 rabi (wet) season. Wheat cultivar PBW 343 was planted on 28 Nov 1996 in 20-cm rows. Phosphorus was applied at the rate of 26.4 kg P ha⁻¹. Nitrogen was applied in four replicates (see table).

SPAD readings were taken at MT on 30 Jan 1997. Ten plants per plot were read, consisting of three readings per leaf.

Grain yield increased linearly from 3.3 to 4.6 t ha⁻¹ with basal-plus-CRI-N rates of 60-120 kg N ha⁻¹. Response of grain yield to MT N ranged from -0.12 to 0.95 t ha⁻¹ on plots that received 120 and 60 kg N ha⁻¹ of basal plus CRI N, respectively.

Grain yield from plots that did not receive MT N correlated positively with SPAD readings at MT ($R^2 = 0.65$, data not shown). When grain yield response to MT N was regressed against SPAD readings, the relationship was negative (see figure; $R^2 = 0.60$). The LSD for grain yield at P=0.05 for the difference between the 0 and 30 kg N ha⁻¹ MT N treatments was 0.20. This minimum significant grain yield response corresponds to a SPAD reading of 44.0 (see figure). So if the SPAD reading at MT is less than 44, a topdressing of 30 kg N ha⁻¹ should be applied because a response is expected. If the SPAD reading is greater than 44, then no response to N is expected. This procedure needs to be repeated for additional seasons and sites to see how robust the critical SPAD reading at MT of 44 is. ■

Nitrogen treatments used in the study.

Treatment	Basal N (kg ha ⁻¹)	CRI N (kg ha ⁻¹)	Basal N + CRI N (kg ha ⁻¹)	MT N (kg ha ⁻¹)	Total N applied (kg ha ⁻¹)
1	0	0	0	0	0
2	30	30	60	0	60
3	30	30	60	30	90
4	40	40	80	0	80
5	40	40	80	30	110
6	50	50	100	0	100
7	50	50	100	30	130
8	60	60	120	0	120
9	60	60	120	30	150

Relationship between wheat grain yield response to N at maximum tillering (MT N) and SPAD readings.